

Enhanced field-effect control of single-layer WS₂ optical features by hBN full encapsulation

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ABSTRACT

The field-effect control of the electrical and optical properties of two-dimensional (2D) van der Waals semiconductors (vdW) is one important aspect in this novel class of materials. Thanks to their reduced thickness and decreased screening, electric-fields can easily penetrate in 2D semiconductor and thus modulate their charge density and their properties. In literature, the field-effect is routinely used to fabricate atomically thin field-effect transistors based on 2D semiconductors. Apart from the tuning of the electrical transport, it has been demonstrated that the field-effect can also be used to modulate the excitonic optical emission of 2D transition metal dichalcogenides such as MoS₂ or WSe₂. In this paper we present some recent experiments on the field-effect control of the optical and excitonic properties of monolayer WS₂. Using the deterministic transfer of van der Waals materials we fabricate planar single-layer WS₂ devices contacted by a gold electrode and partially sandwiched between two insulating hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) flakes. Thanks to the device planar nature we can access optically both the hBN encapsulated and the unencapsulated WS₂ regions and compare the field-effect control of the exciton population in the two cases. We find that the encapsulation strongly increases the range of tunability of the optical emission of WS₂ allowing to tune the photoluminescence emission from a excitons dominated to a trions dominated one. We also discuss how the full encapsulation of WS₂ with hBN helps in reducing spurious hysteretic effects in the field-effect control of the optical properties, similar to what has been reported for 2D vdW field-effect transistors.

Keywords: van der Waals materials, WS₂, hBN, photoluminescence, excitons.

Introduction

In recent years, atomically thin semiconducting transition metal dichalcogenides (2D-TMDs) emerged as an appealing platform for the room temperature implementation of excitonic systems. The reduced dimensionality, which characterizes 2D-TMDs in the monolayer regime, results in a strong confinement of the charge carriers and

39 reduced dielectric screening inducing strong Coulomb interaction with reported exciton binding energy up to 1
40 eV.¹⁻³ This allows for the room temperature optical response to be dominated by the physics of excitons.⁴ These
41 peculiarities have attracted a great deal of interest and are underpinning several appealing phenomena including
42 many-body states,^{5,6} spatially separated interlayer excitons in 2D heterostructures,^{7,8} and high temperature exciton
43 condensation in these systems.⁹ The atomically thin nature of 2D-TMDs and their extreme sensitivity to the
44 surrounding conditions offer also an unprecedented playground to influence and control exciton dynamics through
45 external stimuli such as strain engineering,^{10,11} control of the dielectric environment¹² and application of electric-
46 field.¹³

47 In the key challenge of manipulating the exciton physics of 2D-TMDs, electric-field control has established as a
48 promising and straightforward approach to modulate charge density in atomically thin materials and thus an
49 effective tool to control both the electrical and the optical properties of 2D-TMDs. Indeed, due to the high excitons
50 binding energies that allows for stable excitons at room temperature, the tuning of charge density in 2D-TMDs
51 results in the generation of charged exciton bounded states apart from the neutral ones.¹⁴ As a result, intrinsically
52 n-doped 2D-TMDs, exhibit not only the charge-neutral exciton feature (X_0), but also a lower energy resonance
53 corresponding to negative trions (X^-) that consist of two electrons and one hole bound together through Coulomb
54 interactions.¹⁴ Apart from the intrinsic doping, these optical features can be further effectively modulated by
55 electrical doping.^{15,16} The effective tuning of the charge carriers population of 2D-TMDs through an electric-field
56 relies on the quality of the interface between the 2D-TMD monolayer and the gate dielectric oxide (usually SiO_2) in
57 a field-effect transistor (FET) device configuration. Indeed, the presence of trap states at the 2D-TMD/ SiO_2 interface
58 strongly impact the stability of device operation and the overall device performances giving rise to threshold
59 voltage instability in FETs.¹⁷⁻¹⁹

60 Herein, we have investigated the role of the hBN encapsulation in improving the gate-dependent optical properties
61 of TMDs single-layer integrated in a single-electrode back-gated device, with a particular focus on the optical
62 properties of WS_2 . Interestingly, we found that similarly to FETs also the field-effect control of the optical
63 properties of single-layer WS_2 can be strongly affected by traps, which introduce gate voltage hysteresis in the
64 optical response and reduce the tunability of the excitons population. In this paper, we demonstrate that the full
65 encapsulation of WS_2 greatly enhances the optical tunability of the WS_2 photoluminescence (PL) in response to an
66 external electric-field provided by the back-gate, resulting in improved modulation of X_0 and X^- PL peaks intensity
67 and in an increase of the energy separation between the X_0 and X^- PL peaks. In addition, we found that full
68 encapsulation of WS_2 with insulating hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) also improves the field-effect control by
69 reducing spurious hysteretic effects with beneficial effect on the tunability of the optical emission of WS_2 , thanks
70 to the effective decoupling of the charge traps mediated by the hBN interlayer.²⁰ In general, hBN encapsulation is
71 shown to lead to an enhancement of 2D WS_2 optical quality by offering a protection against unwanted doping
72 contributions from substrates and chemicals or physical adsorbates from the environment, resulting in cleaner
73 spectra characterized by sharper emission from neutral and charged exciton.²¹

74 **Results and discussions**

75 Figure 1a shows an optical microscopy picture of the fabricated device used to investigate the electric-field
76 dependence of the exciton features of bare and encapsulated WS_2 single-layer (1L- WS_2). The WS_2 based device
77 consists of a partially encapsulated hBN/single-layer WS_2 /hBN heterostructure layered on top of a SiO_2 /Si
78 substrate (SiO_2 thickness 290 nm). We used a single gold electrode geometry in which the electrode is in direct
79 contact with the WS_2 monolayer and the doping density can be varied by applying a voltage between the Si back-
80 gate and the gold electrode (Figure 1b). Single-layer WS_2 and hBN flakes were mechanically exfoliated (see
81 Supporting Information, section 'Sample Fabrication') and sequentially transferred by an all-dry deterministic
82 transfer procedure on the SiO_2 /Si substrate in contact with a pre-patterned Au electrode by using a

Figure 1. (a) Optical microscope images of the WS₂ based device, the scale bar corresponds to 20 μm . (b) Schematics of the system with highlighted the two different WS₂ regions that can be experimentally accessed. (c) Photoluminescence spectrum of hBN full encapsulated WS₂ monolayer fitted to two peaks corresponding to the emission from neutral excitons (orange curve) and trions (green curve).

83 polydimethylsiloxane stamp (Gel-Film WF x4 6.0mil by Gel-Pak).^{22,23} In particular, a bottom hBN flake (thickness
 84 ~ 40 nm) was placed in close vicinity of the gold electrode and then a WS₂ single-layer was transferred bridging g
 85 the bottom hBN flake and the gold contact. Finally, a top hBN flake (thickness ~ 20 nm) was positioned on top of
 86 the 1L-WS₂/bottom hBN stack, covering only part of the WS₂ flake (Figure 1a). This planar device geometry
 87 provides the great advantage to have in the same device two regions, the encapsulated (highlighted by the green
 88 arrow in Fig. 1b) and the unencapsulated one purple arrow in Fig. 1b), both belonging to the same 1L-WS₂ flake.
 89 This enables a direct understanding of the encapsulation effect and helps avoiding possible WS₂ flake-to-flake
 90 variations.

Figure 2. (a) Photoluminescence spectra of the 1L-WS₂ unencapsulated region recorded at gate voltages between -40V and 40 V. Inset: schematic of the probed region on the 1L-WS₂ based device. (b) Photoluminescence spectra recorded at -40 V, -20 V, 0 V, 20V and 40 V gate voltages fitted each to two peaks coming from exciton (Orange curve) and trion (green) emission.

91 The monolayer thickness of the WS₂ flake was confirmed through differential reflectance measurements
 92 before the heterostructure fabrication²⁴ as well as Raman spectroscopy (see Supporting Information,
 93 section ‘Raman characterization of the sample’ and Figure S1) and by PL spectroscopy of the WS₂
 94 monolayer. As expected, both the differential reflectance and the PL spectrum are characterized by a
 95 main feature at 2.01 eV (respectively in the two cases a dip and a peak) that is indicative of a single-layer
 96 WS₂ flake.^{24,25} Figure 1c shows the PL spectrum of encapsulated WS₂ recorded after the device
 97 fabrication, which is dominated by a prominent peak located at 2.001 eV, slightly redshifted from the
 98 unencapsulated 1L-WS₂, due to the change in the refractive index of the substrate from SiO₂ to hBN.²¹
 99 By a closer inspection one can see that the PL peak is skewed toward lower energies showing a clear
 100 shoulder. In fact, the experimental data can be fitted to two gaussian peaks centred respectively at 2.001
 101 eV and 1.974 eV. These two features are excitonic in nature and can be assigned respectively to the
 102 recombination of excitons and trions at the K point in the band structure of single-layer WS₂ where the
 103 direct bandgap is located.²⁵

104 To investigate the electric-field modulation of the optical properties of WS₂ single-layer and to reveal
 105 the influence of hBN encapsulation, we measured PL emission upon shining a focused laser beam on top
 106 of the bare WS₂ or on the fully encapsulated regions while sweeping the back-gate voltage (V_g) between
 107 40 V and -40 V. In this study all the PL measurements were performed at room temperature by using a
 108 532 nm laser with a low excitation power of 4 μ W, and a laser spot diameter of 1 μ m. Figure 2a shows
 109 the recorded PL spectra of bare 1L-WS₂ acquired at different values of V_g , between -40 V and 40 V.
 110 Similar to Figure 1c, the emission feature of 1L-WS₂ consists of a peak skewed toward lower energy
 111 ascribed to the radiative recombination of neutral excitons and negative trions. As can be observed from
 112 the plot, the total integrated PL intensity of bare 1L-WS₂ is weakly sensitive to the V_g , being enhanced at
 113 negative V_g and reduced at positive V_g . This behaviour is expected for a semiconductor characterized by
 114 an intrinsic n-doping as is the case of 1L-WS₂.^{15,26} The two-components fits of the 40 V, 20 V, 0 V, 20 V

Figure 3. (a) Photoluminescence spectra of the 1L-WS₂ hBN encapsulated region recorded at gate voltages between -40V and 40 V. Inset: schematic of the 1L-WS₂ sample and of the probed region. (b) Photoluminescence spectra recorded at -40 V, -20V, 0 V, 20V and 40 V gate voltages fitted each to two peaks coming from exciton (orange curve) and trion (green) emission.

115 and -40 V PL spectra, presented in Figure 2b, shows the influence of V_g on the X₀ and X⁻ peaks energies
 116 and on the total integrated intensity two peaks.^{15,27} In addition, we investigated the modulation of 1L-
 117 WS₂ excitonic properties, by analysing the differential reflectance spectra as a function of V_g (see
 118 Supporting Information, section ‘Gate dependent differential reflectance spectroscopy’).

119 Differently from the bare 1L-WS₂, the PL features of the hBN fully encapsulated WS₂ single-layer are
 120 more strongly affected from the electric-field as shown in Figure 3a.²⁰ The total integrated intensity
 121 shows an abrupt decrease by sweeping the V_g from -40 V to 40 V indicating the strong tunability of this
 122 parameter in the encapsulated case compared to the unencapsulated one. As can be seen in the fits of
 123 Fig. 3b, at negative V_g the X₀ peak is dominant whereas at positive V_g it becomes almost undetectable
 124 due to the strong charge carriers injection given by the electrical doping.^{28,29} In fact, at 40 V the X- peak

Figure 4. (a) Normalized integrated PL intensities of X and X⁻ peaks versus gate voltage on 1L-WS₂ (left panel) and hBN/WS₂/hBN region (right panel). (b) Emission energy peaks of X and X⁻ versus gate voltage on 1L-WS₂ (left panel) and hBN/WS₂/hBN region (right panel).

125 remains the only prominent feature in the PL spectrum, thus showing an inversion of the excitonic
 126 population from excitons to trions. The shift of both X₀ and X⁻ is also considerably enhanced thanks to
 127 the improved dielectric and traps environment provided by the hBN encapsulation, with a redshift of 30
 128 meV of the X⁻ peak and a blueshift of 16 meV of the X₀ peak at $V_g = 40$ V.^{30,31}

129 Figure 4 shows the results of the two-peaks fits of the PL spectra of bare 1L-WS₂ and hBN fully
 130 encapsulated 1L-WS₂ as a function of V_g . The intensity of the peaks is reported in panel a and the centre
 131 of the peaks in panel b. The peaks intensity shows in both the unencapsulated and encapsulated cases a
 132 decrease when going toward positive gate voltages, but this decrease is shallower in the first case and
 133 more abrupt in the second case. Focusing on the neutral exciton, we can observe that its intensity is
 134 reduced by 50% in the un-encapsulated WS₂ by sweeping the voltage from negative to positive,
 135 nevertheless the X₀ peak is always more intense than the X⁻ peak in the full voltage range. On the other
 136 hand, the X₀ peak intensity of the neutral exciton is reduced by 99% in the encapsulated sample,
 137 moreover the encapsulated case shows an inversion of the dominant peak for voltages larger than 20 V,
 138 indicating that for these voltages the generation and recombination of trions is favoured over the neutral
 139 excitons one.

140 The energies of the peaks in the two 1L-WS₂ regions also show an analogous behaviour, with the
 141 encapsulated case showing a much stronger dependence on V_g than the unencapsulated one, in which
 142 the peaks energies appear almost constant. The sweep of V_g from -40 V to 40 V induces in the
 143 encapsulated case a redshift of almost 30 meV for the X⁻ peak position and a slight blueshift 16 meV
 144 for the X₀ peak. Also the energy splitting between the X₀ and X⁻ remarkably increases in the encapsulated
 145 case when sweeping V_g from -40 V to 40 V resulting in an energy separation that goes from 20 meV to
 146 66 meV, which in this latter case is about five times higher than in the bare 1L-WS₂. Interesting, the full
 147 encapsulation enables an improved field-effect control considering that, in previous reports that

148 exploited the electric-field control of the optical properties of bare WS₂, a maximum splitting of 34 meV
 149 has been achieved only by using very high operational voltages.^{27,31} It is worth noting that both the X₀
 150 and X- peaks are initially redshifted because of the encapsulation as previously reported.³² In literature,
 151 the energy splitting between X and X- has been defined as the dissociation energy of trions, which in the
 152 case of constant trion binding energy is mainly dependent on the Fermi level position.¹⁶ The energy
 153 splitting thus increases when increasing the electron doping as a consequence of the rising of the Fermi
 154 level (see Figure 4b).^{15,33} On the other hand, the blueshift of the exciton energy is ascribed to a reduction
 155 of the exciton binding energy resulting from electron doping.^{16,34} Thus, the enhanced energy splitting
 156 between X₀ and X- reported in the case of the fully hBN encapsulated WS₂ represents clear evidence of
 157 the more effective electrical doping of the 1L-WS₂ and the enhanced field-effect control enabled by the
 158 hBN full encapsulation.

159 To gain insight in the field-effect control of the optical properties of single-layer WS₂ and to further
 160 investigate the advantage of hBN encapsulation, we also performed a full gate sweep measurement,
 161 which consists of forward and reverse sweeps first from 0 V to 50 V, then from 50 V to -50 V and finally
 162 sweeping back from -50 V to 0 V, with a gate voltage changing rate of 0.6 V/s and focusing on the
 163 emission of the neutral exciton X₀. Figure 5a shows the intensity of the X₀ peaks in the two 1L-WS₂ when
 164 performing this full gate sweep. As can be seen, the curves do not overlap in the forward and backward
 165 V_g sweep. Nevertheless, this non-ideal hysteretic behaviour is remarkably reduced when considering
 166 the PL emission of the hBN/WS₂/hBN region. In detail, the encapsulation by few layers hBN induces a
 167 52% reduction of the hysteresis thanks to the effective decoupling of the charge traps and atmosphere
 168 adsorbates from the 1L-WS₂. However, even with hBN encapsulation the hysteresis is not completely
 169 suppressed. This could be due to the presence of residual impurities (*i.e.* PDMS residues and/or water
 170 molecules) unintentionally introduced during the fabrication process or to defects and traps intrinsic to
 171 the WS₂ crystal.²⁰

Figure 5. (a) Comparison of the gate-dependent optical hysteresis of the X₀ peak integrated intensity in 1L-WS₂ (magenta) and hBN/1L-WS₂/hBN (green curve). (b-c) Comparison of the hysteresis with different back-gate voltage sweep rates for X₀ intensity in 1L-WS₂ (b) and in hBN/WS₂/hBN (c) at 0.6 V/s and at 1.6 V/s.

172 Finally, we have investigated the optical hysteresis at different V_g sweep rates. Figure 5b and 5c show
173 the neutral exciton PL peak intensity recorded from the bare 1L-WS₂ and hBN/WS₂/hBN obtained
174 applying two different back-gate sweep rates, namely 0.6 V/s and 1.6 V/s for the full gate sweep
175 measurement. We observe the overall trend of reduced hysteresis as the sweep rate decrease; however,
176 the behaviour is different in the bare and the fully encapsulated 1L-WS₂ regions. While the bare 1L-WS₂
177 exhibits a hysteresis that is almost not influenced by the speed, showing only a slight reduction
178 estimated in 19% of the hysteresis voltage window, in the hBN/WS₂/hBN, the hysteresis at 0.6 V/s
179 sweep rate is significantly lower if compared to the 1.6 V/s rate showing a reduction of 59%. This
180 suggests that in the latter case the traps present in the system are more short-lived and less detrimental
181 for the overall optical tunability and field-effect control.

182 **Conclusions**

183 In conclusion, we demonstrated the tuning of excitonic emission in monolayer WS₂ exploiting an
184 externally applied electric-field in a single-electrode device. We considered both bare and hBN fully
185 encapsulated WS₂ single-layer and we found that the hBN encapsulation greatly enhances the optical
186 tunability in response of the electric-field. In details, the PL response of the full hBN encapsulated WS₂
187 monolayer change dramatically resulting in an increase of the energy splitting between neutral excitons
188 and trions from 20 meV at -40 V up to 66 meV for voltages of 40 V, as the Fermi level rises. In addition,
189 the enhanced effect of doping enabled by the full encapsulation, allows to fully suppress the neutral
190 exciton generation and recombination at positive voltages resulting in a PL spectrum completely
191 dominated by trions emission. The hBN encapsulation is also effective in reducing the hysteresis
192 observed in the voltage-dependent PL providing an adequate protection from the trap states that can be
193 present for example at the interface between SiO₂ and WS₂. These findings demonstrate that field-effect
194 control combined with hBN encapsulation represents a practical approach to control and/or enhance
195 the radiative excitonic emission in single-layer WS₂ at room temperature toward improved exciton-
196 based optoelectronic applications.

197

198 **Supporting Information:** Supplementary information includes: Sample Fabrication, Raman
199 characterization of the sample, Gate dependent differential reflectance spectroscopy.

200

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Supporting Information: enhanced field-effect control of single-layer WS₂ optical features by hBN full encapsulation

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Sample fabrication

Single-layer WS₂ and few-layer hBN flakes were mechanically exfoliated from bulk crystals with Nitto SPV 224 tape and transferred onto the surface of a Gel-Film (Gel-Pak WF ×4 6.0 mil) substrate. Then single-layer flakes of WS₂ were identified on the PDMS stamp with an optical microscope operated in transmission mode¹ and their thickness confirmed by differential reflectance.

Synthetic bulk WS₂ crystals were purchased from HQ Graphene.

Bulk hBN crystals were grown by K. Watanabe and T. Taniguchi.²

Raman characterization of the sample

Figure S1 shows the Raman signals coming from single-layer WS₂ (between 200 cm⁻¹ and 500 cm⁻¹) and hBN (between 1200 cm⁻¹ and 1500 cm⁻¹). The top panels have been recorded on bare WS₂ and bare hBN regions while the bottom panels have been measured in the hBN/WS₂/hBN stack region. The spectra collected on the WS₂ monolayer show typical Raman feature for this 2D material.³ For laser excitation of 532 nm, the Raman spectrum is dominated by the 2LA mode at ~ 352 cm⁻¹, E_{12g} at ~356 cm⁻¹ and A_{1g} at ~ 418 cm⁻¹.

Regarding hBN, the Raman spectrum is dominated by E_{2g} peak at 1362 cm⁻¹.

Gate dependent differential reflectance spectroscopy:

In order to verify the tunability of the optical properties by means of the electric-field, preliminary gate-dependent differential reflectance measurements were carried out on the devices.

310 For this measurements, the device is mounted under the objective of an optical microscope (Motic
 311 BA310 Met-T) system supplemented with a homebuilt micro-reflectance module based on a fiber-
 312 coupled CCD spectrometer (CCS200/M, Thorlabs).⁴ The differential reflectance spectrum was
 313 calculated as $(R-R_0)/R$, where R is the intensity reflected by the flake, R_0 the intensity reflected by the
 314 substrate.⁵ The absorbance spectra show two main peak features at 2.02 eV and 2.4 eV, respectively
 315 associated to direct band gap transitions at the K point of the Brillouin zone that generates excitons
 316 labelled A and B,⁶ but Figure S2 focuses mainly on the characteristics of exciton A, which is also
 317 prominent in photoluminescence.⁷

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319 **Figure S1.** Room-temperature Raman spectra from the unencapsulated monolayer WS₂ region (top
 320 left), from the bottom hBN (top right) and from the hBN/WS₂/hBN stack region (bottom left and
 321 bottom right), using a 532 nm laser excitation. The main peaks due to WS₂ and hBN have been labeled.

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324 **Figure S2.** (a) Differential Reflectance spectra of the 1L-WS₂ sample at the back-gate voltages between -40V and
 325 40 V. (b) Differential reflectance intensity of the A peak versus gate voltage. (c) Gate-dependent optical hysteresis
 326 the for A peak differential reflectance intensity in 1L-WS₂ FET.

327 Figure S2a shows the differential reflectance spectra of WS₂FET under gate voltages, namely -40 V, 0 V
328 and 40 V. We observed an overall reduction of the optical absorbance in correspondance of the A peak
329 by increasing electron doping. Moreover, this effect is also accompanied by a red shift of the main peak.

330 Fig S2b shows, the intensity variation of the peak as a function of voltage ranging from -40 V and 40 V
331 with a step voltage of 10 V. We also observed the hysteresis behaviour in the differential reflectance
332 performing a full gate sweep from -50 V to 50 V (Figure S2c). It is worth to note that was not possible to
333 appreciate a reflectance signal on the WS₂ single-layer encapsulated with hBN, due to thin film
334 destruvtive interference related to the thicknesses of hBN and SiO₂ that strongly influence the visibility
335 of exciton resonances in absorption measurements.⁸

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Graphical TOC: enhanced field-effect control of single-layer WS₂ optical features by hBN full encapsulation

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